

Calculation of Crack Width and Strength of Ferrocement in Axial Tension

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SUMMARY

In this paper, the calculation formulas of the crack width and the strength of ferrocement in axial tension have been established. These formulas are fitted in the experimental results. They can be used to calculate not only the strength of ferrocement in each working stage, but the initial visible crack width and the crack width under a certain stress as well.

INTRODUCTION

According to the reinforcement form which is mostly used in the fields of building construction, hydraulic structure and shipbuilding industry, 81 ferrocement slabs of 27 sets with various thickness of slabs and reinforcement content have been tested, and the calculation formulas of the crack width and the strength of ferrocement in axial tension have been established.⁽¹⁾

All the tests are conducted on an auto-control loading tester with a special clamping apparatus which is able to adjust the sample in two-direction, when it is eccentric. The mechanical characteristic of ferrocement slab is shown in Fig. 1. It characterizes the stages of elasticity, crack forming, crack developing and rupture, we regard the corresponding stress in each stage as the strength index in each stage.

CALCULATION OF THE CRACK WIDTH AND THE CRACK SPACE OF FERROCEMENT

Calculation of the Crack Space

Under axial tensile loading, after the cracks of ferrocement slab occurred, the stresses on the component materials re-distribute. The stress at the cross section of mortar where the crack has occurred reduces to Zero. The external force is carried by the steel bars and wire meshes, and it is transmitted by the bond between the surface of reinforcement and mortar to parts of mortar where cracks have not occurred. The process is shown in Fig. 2. The region between two cracks, where the shear stress is transmitted by bars and meshes is divided into two parts: l_1 and l_2 . l_1 is the bond region, and T_{nmax} represents the ultimate bond strength. Value l_1 is related to the surface texture of steel bars, specific circumference coefficient of reinforcement and bond between steel bars and mortar. l_2 is the sliding region where the bond is destroyed, but the friction force of shearing resistance T_m still exists. l_2 is related to the specific circumference of reinforcement K and the stress of steel bars and meshes. In a sample, K is a constant, but the strength of mortar in different region has a

little variation due to ununiformity of mortar. When the load increases from N_1 (when the cracks occur) to N_3 (at that time, the number of cracks do not increase any more), l_1 changes only a little, because the ultimate shearing deformation between steel bars and mortar at the part where τ_{nmax} exists is rather small and its variation is small too. However, l_2 changes largely, because τ_m could not change, in order to keep the stress difference produced due to the increasing of stress of the steel bars and meshes within l_2 , l_2 must increase. Therefore, accompanied with increasing of the stress on the steel bars and meshes, $l_1 + l_2$ increases, while the crack space decrease. The probably maximum value of the shearing stress transmission region is equal to the minimum value of the crack spaces. Only when the number of cracks does not increase any more, the total shear force which is transmitted in the region of $l_1 + l_2$ becomes maximum, and $l_1 + l_2$ can be corresponded with the probably minimum value of the crack spacing, L_f . Generally, the maximum value of the crack space is not more than twice of $l_1 + l_2$. When the load reaches N_4 , for satisfying the coordinated condition of deformation, l_1 must be decreased, and the stress τ_{nmax} on the steel bars and l_2 must be increased (but l_2 can not be increased too much). The total transmitted shear force begins to decrease (the bond between the yielded steel bars and mortar are all destroyed). When the number of cracks does not increase any more, L_f is chiefly related to μ/d and the surface texture of steel bars and wire meshes. We can choose $K = \mu/d$ as a basic parameter to establish the relationship between L_f and K . When the crack width is 0.05 mm, the experimental curve between L_f and K is shown in Fig. 3. It can be expressed as following:

$$\bar{L}_f = 1.35 + 0.73 / (K - 0.066) \quad (1)$$

$$K = \mu_1 / d_1 + \mu_2 / d_2 + \dots + \mu_n / d_n \quad (2)$$

Experiments show that, on the sample reinforced with transverse bars, generally, the cracks occur at the position where the transverse steel bars exist, the calculated value of L_f must be equal to or less than the space between two transverse bars.

Calculation of Crack Width

General Formula of the Crack Width. The crack width is produced due to the relative sliding between reinforcement and mortar, it can be regarded as the elongation difference between reinforcement and mortar within the shearing transmission region of two sides of crack.

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = \bar{\epsilon}_g \bar{L}_f - \bar{\epsilon}_s \bar{L}_f \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4. shows the variation of the stress distribution of steel bars and mortar in the region of L_f when the loading is increasing. In the region of L_f , the average stress on steel bars and wire meshes is:

$$\bar{\sigma}_g = \sigma_g - \omega \sigma_g'$$

From the coordinate condition of internal forces at the cross section of middle part between two cracks, we can find that the decreased internal force of steel bars is equal to the increased internal force of mortar:

$$\sigma_g' = \sigma_{SL} A_s / A_g$$

During the process of cracking, $\sigma_{SL} = \beta R_{bL}$, $\sigma = \sigma_g \mu$, and $\alpha_s = \beta \omega$. Thus, we can easily obtain the relationship between the average crack width and the average stress of ferrocement as following:

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = (\sigma - \alpha_s (1 + \eta \mu_0) R_{bL}) \bar{L}_f / \mu_0 E_g \quad (4)$$

If the ferrocement slab is reinforced by over two kinds of different elastic modulus of steel bars and meshes, the value of μ can be converted into the percentage of reinforcement of wire meshes, according to the ratio of elastic modulus.

The calculated value from formula (4) is the average value of the crack width produced by elastic deformation of steel bars and meshes. However, the maximum crack width is very important for the engineering practice. The crack width consists of two parts of deformation. One part is the elastic deformation, another part is the sliding deformation caused by parts of bond is destroyed.

From experiments, the ratio of the maximum crack width and average crack width is about 1.5 (In common reinforcement concrete, the ratio is about 2.5⁽²⁾). Therefore, the crack width influence coefficient α must be considered:

(5)

Formula (5) is the general expression formula of the maximum crack width of ferroement slab in axial tension.

The Determining of Coefficients α_s and α . From Fig. 4. we can find that, accompanied with the increase of loading and sliding region l_2 , the value of ω decreases, while the value of β increases. As showing in Fig. 3, the stress distribution curve in region l_1 can be regarded as a cubic parabola, while the stress distribution curve in region l_2 can be regarded as a straight line. Because $\tau_m < \tau_{nmax}$, the value of ω is equal to or less than 0.75, while β is more than 1. Therefore, we can regard α_s , the product of ω and β as a constant, and equals 0.75. Prior to the number of crack is not increased, the transmitted shear does not decrease. At that time, the value of $\omega\beta$ is related to the strength of mortar and the surface texture of steel bars, and it is hardly related to the reinforcement coefficient. Therefore, α_s of ferroement slabs in various reinforced form are nearly the same and equals 0.75. In fact, after the cracks occurred, the ratio of the average deformation of mortar and the total deformation of slab is very small. Since the value of α_s varies very small, its influence on the calculated result from formula (5) is very liminary.

When the crack width equals 0.05 mm, the experimental relationship between $\sigma - 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL}$ and $5 \times 10^{-3} E_{g1} \mu_0 / \bar{l}_f$ is shown in Fig. 5. This relationship curve is a straight line, and the slope of this line is 0.46.

Experiments show that, after the cracks occurred, and prior to the steel bars are yielded, the relationships between the stress and strain of samples are straight lines. We can consider that, in any cases of crack width, the value of α of various percentage of reinforcement are nearly the same. For easy to calculate, after the cracks occurred, the value of α may adopt 0.46.

Calculation Formula of the Maximum Crack Width. Let $\alpha = 0.46, \alpha_s = 0.75$, and substitute them into formula (5), we can obtain the calculation formula of the maximum crack width of ferroement slab in axial tension as following:

$$\delta_{fmax} = 2.04 [\sigma - 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL}] \bar{l}_f / E_{g1} \mu_0 \quad (6)$$

We must notice that, formula (6) only fit in the condition prior to the steel bars and wire meshes are yielded.

CALCULATION OF THE STRENGTH OF FERROEMENT SLAB IN AXIAL TENSION

Calculation of the Strength in Each Stage of Cracking

From formula (5), we can obtain the general calculation formula of the strength of ferroement in axial tension when the crack width is maximum, as following:

$$\sigma_{fmax} = 0.46 \delta_{fmax} E_{g1} \mu_0 / \bar{l}_f + 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL} \quad (7)$$

When the crack width equals 0.05mm or 0.1mm respectively, the calculation formulas of the strength of ferroement in axial tension are:

$$\sigma_{0.05} = 2.3 \times 10^{-3} E_{g1} \mu_0 / \bar{l}_f + 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{0.01} = 4.6 \times 10^{-3} E_{g1} \mu_0 / \bar{l}_f + 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL} \quad (9)$$

From the balance condition of internal forces at the crack and the middle section between two cracks, the stresses of various reinforcement at the cross section of crack is obtained and shown in Fig. 6. These stresses must not be more than the yielding of each reinforcement materials. They are controlled according to the following formulas:

$$\sigma_{g1} = 0.46 \delta_{fmax} E_{g1} / \bar{l}_f + 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL} K_1 / K \mu_1 \leq R_{g1} \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{g2} = 0.46 \delta_{fmax} E_{g2} / \bar{l}_f + 0.75 (1+n\mu_0) R_{bL} K_2 / K \mu_2 \leq R_{g2} \quad (11)$$

Calculation of the Strength When the Steel Bars Are Just Yielded.

Considering the balance condition of internal forces in the middle section between two cracks and at the cross section of the crack, the strength of the slab when a certain steel bar is yielded at the cross section at the crack can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = R_{gi} \mu_o / n_{gi} + 0.75(1+n\mu_o)(1-K_i \mu_o / K\mu_{io}) \quad (12)$$

Calculation of the Initial Crack

From the elastic stage to the elastoplastic stage, the relationship between the stress and the strain of ferrocement in axial tension has three cases. Accompanied with the change of reinforcement condition, the initial crack strength is quite different. It is very important to mirror the stress state exactly by calculating for understanding the properties of ferrocement and using the component materials reasonably.

Calculation of Crack Resistance Strength. The crack resistance of ferrocement which has or has not the transverse steel bars, σ_{kf} or $\bar{\sigma}_{kf}$ can be calculated by the following formulas respectively:

$$\sigma_{kf}' = (1+n\mu_o - \sum d_i' / h) R_{bL} \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{kf} = 1.2(1+n\mu_o) R_{bL} \quad (14)$$

In formula (14), the constant 1.2 is considered that the uniformity of mortar has been improved by reinforcement of wire mesh. Due to the stress concentration on the transverse steel bars, there is not the constant 1.2 in formula (13)

Calculation of the Strength When the Visible Crack Occurs. From formula (7), the calculation formula of the strength when the crack width is 0.01mm can be obtain as the following:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{0.01} = 0.46 \times 10^{-3} E_{g1} \mu_o / \bar{L}_f + 0.75(1+n\mu_o) R_{bL} \quad (15)$$

Comparing formula (14) with formula (15), there are three cases:

the first case: when $\bar{\sigma}_{0.01} > \sigma_{kf}$, we can let $\bar{\sigma}_c = \bar{\sigma}_{0.01}$,

the second case: when $\bar{\sigma}_{0.01} < \sigma_{kf}$, we can let $\bar{\sigma}_c = \sigma_{kf}$,

the third case: when $\bar{\sigma}_{0.01} = \sigma_{kf}$, we can let $\bar{\sigma}_c = \bar{\sigma}_{0.01} = \sigma_{kf}$.

The first case appears only when the percentage of reinforcement is high and the dispersion in ferrocement is rather good. In this case, the initial crack width is less than 0.01mm, at first, there is a stage of micro-crack during loading. Then, the micro-cracks, expand to the visible crack gradually. The turning point of the curve of the stress and the strain is rather gentle. Show in Fig. 7(a).

The second case occurs in the sample whose μ and K both are small. It shows that when crack width reaches 0.01mm, the increased internal stress of the steel bars is not enough to balance the discharge of mortar which is caused by rupture of mortar. At that time, in order to keep the balance of external load, the crack width must increase, thus, the stress on steel bars increases. This characteristic of the relationship between the stress and the strain is shown in Fig. 7(b).

In the third case, when the crack width is 0.01mm, the increased stress on the steel bars just keep balance with the discharge of mortar caused by its rupture. The cracking stress equals the strength when the crack width is 0.01mm. The width of the visible crack which just appear is just equal to 0.01mm. The curve between the stress and the strain is a horizontal line. Shown in Fig. 7(c).

Experiments show that the transverse steel bars have great effect on the initial cracking. Generally, in that case, cracks first occur at the part where the transverse bars exist. When μ and K are both rather large, some micro-cracks first appear at the part where the transverse bar is placed. With the increase of load, the micro-cracks expand and become visible cracks. Then, the developing of cracks is not affected by transverse bars. i.e. at that time, the cracks do not occur regularly at the position of the transverse bar and the maximum crack width may not be at the position of transverse bar. The initial crack strength corresponding with each stage of this cracking process can be calculated as below.

The crack resistance strength can be calculated by formulas (13) and (14). When the crack width equals 0.01mm, the strength at the cross section without the transverse bar can be calculated by formula (15). The position of the transverse bars equals 0.01mm can be calculated by the following formula:

(16)

Comparing the formulas (13), (14), (15) and (16), the initial cracking strength of ferrocement with transverse bars, σ_{kf}' , can be determined in the following three cases:

when $\sigma_{o.o}' \geq \sigma_{kf}'$, we can let $\sigma_{cf}' = \sigma_{o.o}'$,
 when $\sigma_{o.o}' \leq \sigma_{kf}'$, we can let $\sigma_{cf}' = \sigma_{kf}'$,
 when $\sigma_{kf}' > \sigma_{o.o}' > \sigma_{kf}'$, we can let $\sigma_{cf}' = \sigma_{o.o}'$.

Calculation of Rupture Strength

Experiments show that, if the steel bars have the obvious yielding point, at first, the steel bars are yielded, then the slab is broken. If the steel bars have not the obvious yielding, probably, the steel bars and the wire meshes are broken by tensile load at the same time. The rupture strength σ_p can be calculated by the following formula:

(17)

When the steel bars have not the obvious yielding point, we can let R equal its rupture strength.

Compare the Calculated Values with the Experimental Results of the Strength in Each Stage

The calculated values and the experimental results of the strength in each stage are all shown in the table. The calculated values are calculated according to the data of the actual properties of component materials, the actual size of samples and the thickness of the coverage.

CONCLUSION

1. The forming and development of the cracks of ferrocement in axial tension is related to the percentage of reinforcement μ , specific circumference coefficient of reinforcement K, the strength of mortar R_{bl} , the thickness of the coverage, and the reinforced form. The initial visible crack width is determined by μ and K. Not all the ferrocement slabs have the stage of micro-cracks. When μ and K are small, the width of initial crack is more than 0.01mm. Only when μ and K are larger than a certain value, the stage of micro-crack can appear. In this case, the micro-cracks expand to be the visible cracks with the increase of load. Ferrocement has large reinforcement dispersion which increase the bonding surface between the component materials. Since the transmitted region of the maximum shear force (i.e. the minimum space between two cracks) decreases, the number of cracks increases, the process of cracking is delayed, and the crack width decreases, its ability of cracking resistance is enhanced.
2. In this paper, the process of cracking is analysed. Cracking is related to the length of shear force transmission region and the stresses of the reinforcement materials, but it is related little to the variation of the number of cracks. The reason that mortar withdraws from work with increase of the stress of the reinforcement materials is explained clearly.
3. On the base of above conception, the calculation formulas of the crack width and the strength of ferrocement in axial tension have been established. They conform to the experimental result well. These formulas can be used to calculate not only the strength in each stage, but also the crack width under a certain stress and the initial visible crack width. According to the requirement of the strength and the initial visible crack width in the engineering, these formulas can be used to determine the minimum percentage of reinforcement.
4. Formulas in this paper, the influences of the coverage and the condition of reinforcement distribution are not to be reflected fully. The distribution of the bonding force between the component materials and their quantitative relationship are not to be studied in detail. These problems must be investigated further.

Comparing the Calculated Values with Experimental Results
of the Strength of Ferrocement in Axial Tension

Number of Sample	Reinforcement form	R_{b1} (kg/cm ²)	Experimental Value/ Calculated Value(kg/cm ²)				σ_g Calculated Value
			σ_{cf}	σ_{005}	$\sigma_{0.1}$	σ_p	
1	2-1 ϕ 4-100	27.5	37.2/37.5	40.7/39.1	60.0/54.3	76.7/83.4	61
2	3-1 ϕ 4-100	31.0	50.5/42.8	55.9/53.1	71.8/79.2	93.1/102.5	72
3	4-1 ϕ 4-100	31.0	43.5/46.0	72.5/59.3	93.5/93.2	113.4/110.1	76
4	4-1 ϕ 6-50	27.5	36.0/46.4	94.8/116.8	130.6/130.8	144.1/160.2	117
5	4-2 ϕ 6-50	31.0	31.7/35.9	68.2/79.0	87.7/92.9	107.1/116.8	88
6	4-3 ϕ 6-100	21.5	33.4/22.8	55.6/54.0	75.1/73.0	90.3/98.7	73
7	4-3 ϕ 6-75	32.5	33.9/42.1	99.0/92.0	106.0/105.0	120.0/124.8	102
8	4-3 ϕ 6-50	32.5	40.7/51.5	111.0/117.5	126.5/127.4	139.8/147.5	120
9	4-3 ϕ 6-25	32.5	92.8/82.0	209.5/202.7	220.0/117.8	241.0/238.4	203
10	4-3 ϕ 8-50	33.5	48.7/62.1	142.1/150.0	155.0/149.0	183.1/166.2	158
11	4-4 ϕ 6-50	32.5	35.7/39.7	73.8/91.4	97.5/105.9	111.8/125.1	102
12	4-5 ϕ 6-100	32.5	29.0/32.2	73.6/62.8	80.3/80.2	94.6/98.6	81
13	4-5 ϕ 6-100	29.5	38.0/33.4	55.5/59.7	82.2/78.2	97.2/97.9	80
14	4-5 ϕ 6-50	32.5	44.4/53.9	121.5/127.6	136.5/138.1	160.0/154.7	129
15	4-5 ϕ 6-25	32.5	79.7/89.4	206.5/230.3	222.0/240.1	253.0/255.3	220
16	5-5 ϕ 6-50	32.5	62.0/52.2	125.0/118.6	135.0/130.1	139.0/147.7	117
17	5-5 ϕ 6-50	29.8	42.4/50.4	121.0/121.9	132.0/132.4	154.0/151.7	123
18	6-5 ϕ 6-50	29.8	41.8/52.1	121.5/128.7	138.0/143.4	155.0/159.0	129
19	6-5 ϕ 6-50	29.8	49.1/46.4	98.2/107.3	129.5/120.8	150.0/140.7	114
20	6-5 ϕ 6-50	29.8	43.0/48.3	108.6/118.3	126.5/128.0	147.0/150.5	120
21	4-3 ϕ 6-50	26.8	55.2/47.5	107.0/108.8	119.0/126.1	124.2/145.4	121
22	4-3 ϕ 6-50	26.8	51.5/46.0	125.8/114.2	131.3/131.0	154.2/150.3	125
23	4-5 ϕ 6-40	26.8	64.5/44.9	102.1/114.3	129.0/131.3	151.6/149.8	125
24	4-5 ϕ 6-25	29.8	65.5/68.8	185.6/182.3	191.1/190.8	217.4/207.7	177
25	6- $\frac{4\phi 3-20}{5\phi 6-100}$	33.8	67.7/47.9	115.4/114.8	135.3/138.3	144.0/168.2	84
26	6- $\frac{4\phi 3-20}{3\phi 6-100}$	29.8	86.1/50.8	134.0/121.2	148.3/140.1	164.0/170.0	101

Note:

In the column of reinforcement form, the numerals and symbols represent individually by order: the layers of meshes - the layers of bars and their diameter - the space between two longitudinal. All the spaces between two transverse bars are 100mm. The meshes are placed outside the bars.

Fig. 1. The relationship between the stress and the strain of ferroconcrete slab in axial tension

Fig. 2. The distribution of bonding force between steel bars and mortar

Fig. 3. The relationship between \bar{L}_f and K

Fig. 4. The stress distribution of steel bars and mortar in the region of L_f

Fig. 5. The relationship curve between $[\sigma - 0.75(1 + n\mu_0)R_{bl}]$ and $[E_g \mu_0 / \bar{L}_f \times 10^{-3}]$

Fig. 6. The stress distribution of different reinforcement materials in the transmission region of shear force

Fig. 7. The characteristic curve between the stress and the strain of ferrocement slab in axial tension during the initial cracking stage

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